

Construct	Measure	Survey Question(s)	Variable Name (component variables are shown in brackets)
<i>Self-concept</i>	Aggregate measure from Likert responses.	Q2	sc_score_ordinal (self_efficacy_understand, self_efficacy_assessment, self_efficacy_career, self_efficacy_good)
<i>Mastery experience</i>	Combination of Leaving Certificate points and the grade achieved in their most recent mathematics module.	Q12 & Q13	Mastery (grade, points)
<i>Growth mindset</i>	<i>fixed vs growth</i>	Q3	Mindset
<i>Peer effect</i>	Impact of peers: <i>very positively/positively/neutral/negatively/ very negatively</i> For modelling, the categories <i>very positively</i> and <i>positively</i> were combined and the categories <i>very negatively</i> and <i>negatively</i> were combined.	Q7	Peers

<i>Lecturer effect</i>	Impact of lecturers: very <i>positively/neutral/negatively/ very negatively</i> For modelling, the categories <i>very positively</i> and <i>positively</i> were combined and the categories <i>very negatively</i> and <i>negatively</i> were combined.	Q7	Lecturer
<i>Perceived difficulty</i>	Perceived difficulty in comparison to other modules: <i>least difficult/similar to other modules/most difficult</i> Treated as a categorical variable for RQ2 with <i>similar to other modules</i> as the reference category. Treated at ordinal for RQ3 with 0 corresponding to the category <i>least difficult</i> , 1 for <i>on par with other modules</i> and 2 for <i>most difficult</i> .	Q5	difficulty
<i>Mathematics performance</i>	Grade achieved in their most recent mathematics module, midpoint of grade band.	Q13	grade
<i>Enjoyment</i>	Enjoyment compared to other modules: <i>most enjoyable/similar to other modules/ least enjoyable/ I didn't enjoy any module</i>	Q4	enjoyment

<i>Utility value</i>	Categorical variable with 6 categories, treated as	Q1	VAM
<i>motivation</i>	binary for the structural equation model (SEM), with “I just want to pass the module” as one category, with all other categories combined into one.		
<i>Pre-university</i>	Leaving Certificate points, midpoint of grade band.	Q12	points
<i>mathematics grade</i>			
